

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPOSITION IN ARTISTIC FINISHING WORKS

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Anotatsiya: Kompozitsiya - o'quv predmet sifatida, xaykaltaroshlik, me'morchilik, grafika, qalamtasvir, rangtasvir, san'at tarixi kabi mutaxassis fanlari bir-biri bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. Qalamtasvir va rang tasvirda rassom bevosita kompozitsiya asoslariga murojaat qiladi, uning qonun-qoidalarini bilmay turib kompozitsiya, qalam tasvir, rang tasvir mohiyatini tushunib yetmaydi.

Kalit so'zlar Kompozitsiya usullari, kompozitsion vositalar, maishiy janr, mahobatli bezakli san'at, pedagogika, badiiy-grafika, frontal kompozitsiya, gorizontal kompozitsiya, vertikal kompozitsiya, diagonal kompozitsiya.

Аннотация: Композиция – как учебный предмет неразрывно связаны такие специальные дисциплины, как скульптура, архитектура, графика, рисунок карандашом, живопись, искусствоведение. В карандашном рисунке и цветном рисунке художник непосредственно обращается к основам композиции, не зная ее правил, нельзя понять суть композиции, карандашного рисунка, цветного рисунка

Ключевые слова: Композиционные приемы, средства композиции, бытовой жанр, монументальное-декоративное искусство, педагогика, художественная графика, фронтальная композиция, горизонтальная композиция, вертикальная композиция, диагональная композиция.

Annotation: Composition - as an academic subject, such special disciplines as sculpture, architecture, graphics, pencil drawing, painting, art history are inextricably linked. In a pencil drawing and color drawing, the artist directly refers to the basics of composition, without knowing its rules, it is impossible to understand the essence of the composition, pencil drawing, color drawing.

Keywords: Compositional techniques, means of composition, everyday genre, monumental and decorative art, pedagogy, artistic graphics, frontal composition, horizontal composition, vertical composition, diagonal composition.

"We mobilize all the forces and opportunities of our state and society in order for our young people to become independent-minded, have high intellectual and spiritual potential and to be able to mature and be happy in the world as people who do not come to their peers in any field. "

SH. M. Mirziyoyev

The word composition means "compositio" from Latin-i.e., comparing pieces of its subjects and placing them in a certain order in a holistic way, creating, articulating, composing in accordance with an idea.

Composition is present on the basis of all types of art: literature, theater-cinema, music, fine and applied art, architecture, etc.

Composition appeared as an educational subject, after pencil drawing, painting, and now the composition course is included in the educational plans of Higher Education, professions.

In the fiction and graphic facts of pedagogical universities, the science of composition, together with the development of students' creative abilities, teaches the laws of composition, methods of expressing reality in the correct form.

In the visual arts, the composition is created by visual means such as pencil, shadow-light, color, air and line perspective.

The composition course is of great importance in the development of figurative thinking in independent creative and pedagogical activity of students.

The science of composition consists of conversation, lectures and practical classes. The composition is perfectly studied by the Basic Rules of law, methods and means, students in the process of practical training and conversations.

Composition-as an educational subject, such specialist disciplines as haicality, architecture, graphics, pencil drawing, painting, art history are inextricably linked with each other. Pencil drawing and color in the image, the artist directly refers to the basics of composition, without knowing its laws, the composition, pencil image, color do not understand the essence of the image.

This composition provides an understanding of the essence of the subject of the teaching manual, the history of its development in the Fine Arts, the Basic Rules of law of artistic creation, tools and recommendations on the methods of teaching them in the artistic and

graphic faculties of pedagogical universities. Therefore, in the training of artists-teachers, it is recommended to study the subject of composition as the most complex and important subject.

Artistic finishing works, like all types of Fine Art, are carried out based on the General Laws of the composition. That is why these works, while requiring sufficient knowledge and skills from the decorator artist, constantly insist on keeping the issues of composition in the center of attention.

In artistic finishing works, there are types of composition: flat, volumetric, with width and depth. All this will have some kind of general quality and character in the implementation of this or that idea.

Frontal composition means the organization of a frontal image by two coordinates. A characteristic feature of the Frontal composition is the limitation of the use of volumetric elements in it and, at the same time, an increase in the possibilities of enlarging its measurements. Therefore, even if some relief images (for example: candelabra, wood and ganch carvings and hacksaws) are built on the laws of plastic, a flat surface belongs to the type of compositions.

Most of the decorative work in educational institutions, for example, visual aids, wall newspapers, thematic stands, invitations, greeting cards, thematic Al'bom, etc., is performed on the basis of a frontal composition.

The construction of the composition will depend on the function and content of the particular object, the purpose for which it is intended. The main structures of the compositions are as follows:

Horizontal composition-in which the elements of the composition are placed on a horizontal surface. For example: Field, city panorama, etc.

Vertical composition is an active, dynamic composition, growing upward, forming a vision of flight, the details of which are located mainly on a steep line.

Diagonal composition – its construction is based on dynamic and intense schemes.

A triangular or pyramidal composition – in this case, a stable, calm state is relied on. The lower part of the surface of the photo is the base of the pyramid.

One of the important features of Frontal compositions is their performance in the form of a thin surface. Frontal composition differs

from other types of compositions in that it gives volume, distance and width.

The volumetric composition comes in the form of three mounts designed for perception from different viewing points.

In accordance with the content and task of the works, some feature of the composition can be exaggerated. The composition, with its properties, ultimately serves as the basis for ensuring the High Artistry of artistic finishing works. In the harmonic integrity of the compositions, colors also acquire special significance. Especially the mosaic panno, in which color occupies the main place, should be taken seriously to the compositional harmony in the stained glass windows. Only then will the color unity of the work be one of the most basic factors affecting aesthetics. Unreasonable deviation from the laws of composition usually reduces both the content and aesthetic nature of artistic finishing works.

If the elements of the composition are located in the same way in relation to each other on the sides, they will be in compositional balance. One of the main issues of composition is combination. On the basis of the combination, New Expressive variants of the composition are prepared by changing the location of one and several elements. Dynamic and stagnant compositions also have their own laws. Between these, it is necessary not to allow the origin of the opposite meaning, that is, to achieve the logical harmony of the main and secondary elements. Knowledge of rhythm cones will greatly help you choose the right character of a rhythmic look when composing an impressive composition.

Artists are charged with such responsibilities as enriching the means of creating artistic images in their works, expanding the scale of their worldview with the experiences of advanced world artists.

A number of important tasks and problems are now facing the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is developing ahead, without deviating from the path of great historical development, which has begun due to its independence.

The future of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is steadily entering the XXI century, is directly related to the development of Science, Education and training. On the basis of the law "on the birth of Education" adopted in 1992, on the basis of the "national program of training of Personnel" adopted in 1997, measures are being implemented to radically reform education in our society. Science,

culture and enlightenment elevate any country to heights, ensuring its progress.

Indeed, today international life, the development of personality have entered such a stage in which advanced technologies, not military power, but intellectual potential, intelligence, thought, are of decisive importance. Now, any state, any nation is strong, first of all, with its high culture and spirituality.

The future of our country directly depends on the training of unconditional personnel. In order to educate a harmonious generation with a new thinking, modern knowledge, to have an organizer and resourceful staff, it is necessary to radically change the educational structure, raise it to the level of demand of the period, become one of the most important tasks of our society, each of us.

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